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FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS IN STUDENTS WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENTS

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Abstract: The article addresses the issues of developing communicative skills in students with hearing impairments. It also highlights the importance of an activity-based approach and a comprehensive methodological approach in the effective development of communicative skills in such students.

Key words: communicative skills, scientific approach, speech activity, communication, psychological adaptation, socialization, pedagogy, methodology, development, directions.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada eshinish qobiliyati zaif o'quvchilarda kommunikativ ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, unda bunday o'quvchilarda kommunikativ ko'nikmalarni samarali rivojlantirishda faoliyatga asoslangan yondashuv va kompleks metodologik yondashuvning ahamiyati ta'kidlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: kommunikativ ko'nikmalar, ilmiy yondashuv, nutq faoliyati, muloqot, psixologik moslashuv, ijtimoiylashuv, pedagogika, metodologiya, rivojlanish, yo'nalishlar.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются вопросы развития коммуникативных навыков у учащихся с нарушениями слуха. Подчеркивается важность деятельностного и комплексного методического подхода в эффективном развитии коммуникативных навыков у таких учащихся.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативные навыки, научный подход, речевая деятельность, общение, психологическая адаптация, социализация, педагогика, методика, развитие, направления.

INTRODUCTION

В статье освещены вопросы развития коммуникативных навыков у учащихся с нарушением слуха. Также подчёркивается, что в эффективном развитии коммуникативных навыков у таких учащихся важную роль играют деятельностный подход и комплексный методологический подход.

- Speech skills (related to mastering speech activity and means of communication);
- Socio-psychological skills (concerning the processes of interaction, expression, manifestation, and influence);
- Psychological skills (self-regulation, mobilization, and mood adjustment);
- The ability to use appropriate speech etiquette rules according to specific communicative situations;
- Effective use of nonverbal means;
- Participation in various forms and levels of communication (dialogue, polylogue, intergroup communication);
- Adherence to moral and cultural norms (consideration of respect, tolerance, and cultural rules in communication).

Researchers interpret communicative skills as an integral part of speech activity. In particular, T.A. Ladyzhenskaya defines communicative skills characteristic of written speech as follows: revealing the topic, expressing the main idea, collecting the necessary materials, systematizing them, constructing the text according to its compositional structure, and expressing thoughts clearly, precisely, and meaningfully [2].

Main Part

From S.L. Soloveichik's point of view, these skills reflect the stages of speech activity such as planning, generating, and controlling thought, and they determine two main directions of communicative skills: speaking and writing (generation of thought) and listening and reading (perception of thought).

In M.R. Lvov's approach, several important stages contributing to the development of oral and written speech are identified: selecting and delimiting the topic, dividing it into subtopics, collecting and systematizing the necessary information, determining the idea and purpose of the composition, developing the composition structure, and editing it. In oral speech, special attention must be paid to orthoepy and expressiveness, while in written speech, adherence to orthography, punctuation, and calligraphy is particularly important [3].

M.T. Baranov interprets communicative skills mainly as abilities aimed at creating a text, listing among them such practical competencies as constructing a text appropriate to the topic, taking into account the purpose, audience, and style, selecting linguistic means, presenting material, and editing it [4].

T.G. Ramzaeva, considering the main components of expressing thought, divides communicative skills into content-related, compositional, figurative-creative, and editing skills [5].

I.M. Mikhaylova, in turn, emphasizes stages such as evaluating the speech situation, defining the purpose, drafting a text plan, selecting linguistic means, and editing the text [6].

In pedagogical literature, other classifications of communicative skills can also be found. For example, L.R. Munirova [7] and B.F. Lomov [8] divide them into three main groups: informational-communicative (transmitting information, understanding the situation), regulatory-communicative (managing communication, inspiring trust), and affective-communicative (emotional response, empathy).

N.G. Terekhova and G.G. Danilenkova [9] associate communicative skills with psychological and pedagogical knowledge, personal qualities, and the ability to overcome barriers in communication.

E.I. Passov [10] distinguishes skills related to active participation in communication. He considers the following particularly important: initiating, maintaining, and concluding a conversation; choosing a strategy; assessing the situation; anticipating the interlocutor's reply; taking the initiative; eliciting a response; and using nonverbal means.

E.A. Bystrova [2], in turn, evaluates communicative skills within the framework of communicative competence and connects them with the ability to select language forms appropriate to communication and to produce dialogic and monologic expressions corresponding to the communicative goals on socio-cultural topics.

An analysis of scientific sources shows that communicative skills are interpreted based on various approaches: activity-oriented, socially role-based, situation-adaptive, and those grounded in the theory of speech activity. In psychological, linguistic, and pedagogical literature, these skills are described as a broad concept, with language skills regarded as their integral component. However, in methodological literature, communicative skills are often equated solely with language abilities.

Therefore, in our research, we interpret communicative skills as a set of complex abilities aimed at effective communication—that is, those that ensure the achievement of specific communicative goals. Within this framework, such activity components as taking into account the interlocutor's point of view, engaging in communication in a spirit of cooperation, and conveying information accurately and clearly play an essential role.

Overall, the various approaches proposed by different authors in the study and classification of communicative skills demonstrate the diversity of theoretical foundations in this field. Most researchers view these skills not merely as aspects of speech, but as a complex system of competencies connected with psychological, social, cultural, and pedagogical dimensions. For this reason, the effective teaching of communicative skills requires a comprehensive and integrative approach.

These skills are formed through interaction and collaboration, adapting to communication contexts, and they ensure successful outcomes in practical communication. Particularly from the perspective of language teaching methodology, it is emphasized that communicative skills should not be limited only to linguistic aspects but should be studied in conjunction with the psychological, social, and cultural factors of communicative activity.

Scientific analyses indicate that communicative skills are not merely abilities related to language or speech, but are also directly connected to a person's psychological state, social experience, and cultural environment. The approaches proposed by researchers allow for a broad analysis of communicative skills within various theoretical frameworks. In the process of studying and developing these skills, each student's personal abilities, needs, and role in communication must be given special attention.

In particular, for students with hearing impairments, the development of communicative skills requires a focus on nonverbal means, empathy, emotional interaction, and social support. Therefore, developing communicative skills in a systematic and integrated manner based on an activity-oriented approach is essential for a student's social adaptation, the ability to express their thoughts freely, and successful participation in communication.

Analysis of the scientific literature shows that existing studies mainly address communicative skills from general pedagogical and linguistic perspectives. However, the communicative needs, individual developmental characteristics, and communication barriers of students with hearing impairments have not been sufficiently studied. Specifically, their psychological state, internal readiness for communication, and adaptive capabilities have not been deeply analyzed in the existing theoretical models.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In our view, for this particular group of students, nonverbal means (facial expressions, gestures, body movements, etc.) deserve special attention in the development of communicative skills. While in most literature nonverbal expression is considered only as an auxiliary tool, for students with hearing impairments, these means serve as a primary communication channel. Nevertheless, the methodological foundations and practical strategies for teaching these tools are still insufficiently developed.

Furthermore, for students with hearing impairments, the use of digital tools and the introduction of visual-interactive technologies in developing communicative skills remain a pressing issue and a subject for further scientific research. In addition, studies focusing on social-emotional competencies, such as empathy, self-awareness, emotional expression, and the confident articulation of one's thoughts, are limited. This limitation is considered a factor restricting successful participation in communication for these students.

Our analysis shows that the relationship between family environment, the level of social support at school, and communicative development also requires in-depth study. A systematic investigation of personal abilities and environmental factors affecting communication is an important direction for introducing scientific novelty.

References

1. Rudensky, E.V. Social Psychology [Text]: Lecture Course / E.V. Rudensky. – Moscow: INFRA-M; Novosibirsk: NGAEiU, 1997. – 224 p.
2. Bystrova, E.A. Communicative Competence in Teaching Russian as a Foreign Language. – Moscow: Russian Language, 2000. – 180 p.
3. Leontiev, A.A. Foundations of Psycholinguistics. – Moscow: Smysl, 2003. – 287 p.
4. Baranov, M.T. Methods of Teaching Russian in School. – Moscow: Akademiya, 2001. – 272 p.
5. Ramzaeva, T.G. Methodical Letter “On the Role of the Textbook ‘Russian Language’ in the Development of Coherent Written Speech of Younger Schoolchildren” [Text] / T.G. Ramzaeva // Primary School, 1995. – No. 8. – P. 66–71.
6. Mikhaylova, I.M. Formation of Communicative Skills of Younger Schoolchildren Using Visual Aids [Text] / I.M. Mikhaylova. – Pskov: PSGPU, 2005. – 188 p.
7. Munirova, L.R. Formation of Communicative Skills in Younger Schoolchildren Through Didactic Play [Text]: Dissertation for the Degree of Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences: 13.00.01 / Leila Rinatovna Munirova. – Moscow, 1993. – 205 p.
8. Lomov, B.F. Methodological and Theoretical Problems of Psychology [Text] / B.F. Lomov. – Moscow: Nauka, 1984. – 448 p.
9. Development of Communicative Skills [Text]: Methodical Recommendations for the Study of the Special Course “Communication” / Comp. G.G. Danilenkova, N.G. Terekhov. – Kaliningrad: Kaliningrad University, 1997. – 31 p.
10. Passov, E.I. Program-Concept of Communicative Foreign Language Education: Development of Individuality in the Dialogue of Cultures [Text] / E.I. Passov. – Moscow: Prosveshcheniye, 2000. – 172 p.

